

**University of
South-Eastern Norway**

The University of South-Eastern Norway CoArA Action Plan

Introduction/background

The University of Southeast-Norway (USN) signed The Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA) in November 2022. A project group was established in early 2023, and a project mandate was prepared. A draft of this mandate was discussed in the USN Research committee, before it was finally decided on by the USN Rectorate and Deans in spring of 2024. The project group consist of employees from the Research department, the HR-department, rector's staff, and academic staff with different backgrounds with regards to field of research and career stages. This involvement of researchers in the project group itself, as well as discussions of drafts with USNs formal bodies such as faculty boards etc, will ensure that the project is carried out in line with the needs and requirements of USNs researchers. During the project period great emphasis will be put on co-creation and dissemination activities such as open dialogue meetings and workshops with individual researchers and research groups. USNs Vice-rector for research is responsible for the project deliverables.

In line with most of the other HE-institutions in Norway, USN has embraced the Norwegian Career Assessment Matrix (NOR-CAM), developed by Universities Norway (UHR – a cooperative body for HE-institutions in Norway). NOR-CAM represents a toolbox for assessment on an individual level, and the principles by which research is evaluated, complies with the principles described in ARRA. The overall intention by UHR, has been that NOR-CAM would be implemented throughout the Norwegian HE-sector, among others with the contribution of the national NOR-CAM network which was established (by UHR) in the summer of 2023. The NOR-CAM network consists of representatives from all HE-institutions in Norway and is recognized as a National Chapter by CoARA.

In the spring of 2024 USN launched an institutional policy for Open Science, which includes a section on research assessment. USNs researchers were heavily involved in preparing this policy, through dialogue with the project group and written contributions to the final text. The process of developing this policy was instrumental in laying the ground for a cultural change towards more open research and new ways of assessing research at USN. Also, during the last couple of years USN has become member in two European university networks/university coalitions – EDUC and Yerun. Within both these networks/coalitions there is great attention directed towards research assessment as such, as well as career development for researchers in the light of reforming research assessment.

The USN action plan is based on the suggested areas of reflection and the following guiding questions, provided by CoARA.

Phase	Reflection Point	Guiding Questions	USN Action Plan	Timeframe
STARTING POINT	1. Reflect on your strategy and change approach	What guiding principles do you (and your community) think are priorities in your approach to reform?	USN will adapt the ARRA and NOR-CAM principles to our university strategy and institutional profile, with an emphasis on mission oriented and open research.	2024 - 2027
		What is the process by which your organisation will work on the reform?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop a project mandate 2. Establish a project group, consisting of employees from the Research department, the HR-department, rector's staff, and academic staff 3. Develop a detailed action plan for the project period as well as a plan for implementation of the reform 4. Develop new criteria and framework for research assessment on individual, group and unit levels 5. Carry out research assessment on all levels using new criteria and frameworks 6. Evaluate new criteria and frameworks 	2024 2024 2024 2025 2026 2027
	2. Involve your institutional community in the change process	How are you planning to involve relevant actor groups (such as researchers at different career stages, research support staff, administrators, and others, depending on the scope of your organisation)?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involving researchers with different kinds of backgrounds, both when it comes to research field, experience and position as members of the project group. • The USN strategic research board will have the role as reference group for the project. • The USN Rectorate and Deans will have the role as steering group for the project. • During the course of the project, USNs employees will be involved through dialogue meetings, as well as be invited to contribute to text (criteria and framework for assessment) that is being developed. • The project will have a dissemination plan and carry out information activities (web pages, SoMe etc) on a regular basis. 	2024 - 2027
		How will you share good practices (internally and with others)?	<p><i>Internally:</i> During the initial project period, the core project group will visit all levels of the organization and arrange both digital and physical meetings, open for everyone. These meetings will be used for information, for sharing good practices, for discussions, for questions etc. Also, in sharing information and good practices, the academic staff members of the extended project group will play an important role. They will share information about the process of reforming research assessment within their own unit and research group.</p> <p><i>Externally:</i> USN will share our experiences with CoARA regularly. Also, USNs membership in other coalitions and university networks such as EDUC and Yerun will contribute to the</p>	2024-2027

			sharing of good practices. There is a lot of interest in the issue of reforming research assessment in the HE-sector in Norway, and most higher education institutions as well as other actors within the research community have signed the ARRA. The implementation of the NOR-CAM toolbox (or institution-adjusted variances of the toolbox) at all institutions will also contribute in this respect, and USN will be an active member of the Norwegian National Chapter (CoARA).	
	3. Identify key challenges to address	Have you identified the Identify key challenges/gaps/bottlenecks/barriers in your organisation with regards to reforming research assessment and the adherence to the action plan? For which does your institution have the power/authority/resources to address?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Cultural change</i> – how various contributions (results, activities and competences) are valued and communicated throughout the institution • <i>Systemic change</i> – using new criteria and indicators used in research assessment, and new forms of best practice, in ad hoc and yearly assessment exercises • <i>Change related to infrastructure</i> – developing new infrastructure needed to document a wide range of results, activities and competences 	2024-2027
		What will be needed to efficiently address them? And what alternatives/strategies can be useful in overcoming some of these challenges?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It will be of major importance to involve both individual researchers, research groups and heads of departments and faculties in the development of new criteria, indicators and framework for research assessment. • A key deliverable from the project is a plan for informing the whole institution about the processes going on and the intended change in research assessment. • Also, resources for developing a new infrastructure necessary for documenting results, activities and competencies, is needed. 	2024-2027
OPERATIONAL ACTION PLAN FOR A 5-YEAR TIME FRAME	4. Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research	How does your organisation plan to enable recognition of more diverse contributions to research?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognition of more diverse contributions to research will be addressed by adapting the NOR-CAM toolbox to USN profile and strategy. • Implementing USNs new Policy for Open Science. • Continue to develop and monitor the activities in USNs newly started mission oriented Strategic Research Areas. • Make sure that Artistic research is a recognized part of the new framework for research assessment, as this is an important part of USN's institutional profile. • Recognize diverse research outputs oriented towards practitioners in various fields (e.g. education-, health- and public sector), such as textbooks, guidelines and co-creation activities, as a part of the new framework. • The framework that is developed must recognize innovation competence in assessment on the individual level, as well as innovation activity and collaboration with society on the unit level. 	2024-2027

		How does your organisation plan to enable greater diversity in career paths and profiles?	<p>Implementing the NOR-CAM toolbox will largely contribute to enabling greater diversity in career paths and profiles. The HR-department will change relevant forms and guidelines used by USN in recruitment processes, as well as forms and guidelines used in the context of application for academic advancement amongst established employees.</p> <p>In 2020 USN was awarded the HR Excellence in Research by the European Commission. The USN action plan for implementing the C&C principles will be revised in accordance with the ARRA and NOR-CAM frameworks.</p>	2024-2025
5. Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators		How does your organisation plan to actively engage in and learn from research on research work?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • USN will be an active member of CoARA and the national NOR-CAM network. • Individual project members will stay up to date on recent developments in research on research evaluation by attending conferences, participating in network meetings, and reading new literature on the topic. • Reports, journal articles etc will be discussed with reference group, and form the basis for the framework that is to be developed. 	2024 -
		How does your organisation plan to accommodate qualitative evaluation mechanisms and base the use of metrics in a way that is aligned with your organisation's value system?	Answering this will be a central part of the project work, and development of a new USN framework for research assessment.	2024-2025
6. Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index		How does your organisation plan to mitigate reliance on JIF and h-index?	<p>JIF and h-index are not really indicators that are used in a systematic way at USN today. However, there is a need for principles and frameworks for how USN should use other quantitative/bibliometric indicators such as publication points and level 1&2 information from the Norwegian publication indicator.</p> <p>Information has to be shared with researchers and leaders on levels at USN about what is, and what is not, appropriate uses of quantitative evaluation mechanisms.</p>	2024-

	7. Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment	How does your organisation plan to mitigate reliance on organisation rankings?	This is not really an issue, given that USN does not rely on, or even relate to, university rankings today.	2024-
	8. Commit resources to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organisational changes committed to	Which resources will your institution allocate to the implementation of the research assessment reform? (Whether in terms of capacity or budget, to actively engage in the reform Journey)	<p>Resources from the Department of Research, Innovation and Library, the HR-department and rector's staff are the main committed resources for the project that will develop new criteria and frameworks.</p> <p>In addition, resources from different faculties/ fields of research will be committed to information about and implementation of the research assessment reform. All are committed in terms of capacity.</p> <p>There is at this point no defined budget allocated for the implementation of the reform.</p>	2024-2025
	9. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes	Does your organisation plan to pilot or implement alternative/new assessment criteria, tools, and processes (e.g. narrative CV format, competency-based CV format, evidence-based CV format, diversification of research careers and associated career progression)?	USN has five mission oriented Strategic Research Areas (SFOs). A system for how to document and evaluate results and activities from the SFOs will be piloted.	2024-2026
	10. Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as	Does your institution plan to provide training, guidance and support to assessment panels, committees, and juries?	Yes, training, guidance and support will have to be provided to assessment panels and committees.	2024-2026

	well as their use			
	11. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition	How does your organisation plan to exchange practices and foster exchange of good practices in national and international contexts?	<p>USN will participate in the following coalitions and networks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CoARA - National NOR-CAM network - YERUN - EDUC 	2024-
	12. Communicate progress made on adherence to the principles and implementation of the Commitments	How will your organisation ensure the transparent communication of the organisation's research evaluation processes within and outside of the organisation?	This will have to be a central component of the communication/dissemination plan that the described project will provide. See also description of project activities above.	2024-2027
	13. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research	How does your institution plan to monitor and (re)evaluate its assessment criteria, tools, and processes? What will be the frequency? Who will be involved in the evaluation?	<p>Assessment criteria, tools and processes will be evaluated after the have been used throughout a full year. The first evaluation process is planned for 2026. Thereafter, assessment frameworks will be reevaluated on a 3-5 yearly basis.</p> <p>The form and process for evaluation has not yet been decided.</p>	2026 -